
HIGH-FIDELITY VOICE CLONING FOR RIOPLATENSE SPANISH

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ABSTRACT

High-fidelity voice cloning requires models capable of reproducing not only linguistic content, but also vocal identity, prosody, rhythm, and the speaker’s regional accent nuances. Most current text-to-speech systems—such as Tacotron2, FastSpeech, or VITS—are optimized for multi-speaker, general-purpose use and rely on textual input without explicit phonological interpretation, which compromises accuracy when aiming to realistically replicate a specific voice.

This work presents a voice cloning system specifically designed for single-speaker training, based on an encoder–attention–decoder architecture operating on Mel spectrograms. The textual input is transformed into a phonetic representation adapted to Rioplatense Spanish through a custom-developed module, published as a Python package. This phonetic transcription applies explicit phonological rules to preserve accents, regional sounds, and dialectal phenomena such as the use of /j/, /ʃ/, /t/, or grapheme neutralization.

One of the main contributions of the model is the incorporation of phoneme-dependent adaptive embeddings, whose values are dynamically modulated based on each phoneme’s relative frequency in the training corpus. This mechanism acts as a form of phonetic-aware regularization, improving the representation of infrequent sounds without requiring large volumes of data.

The model is trained on real audio aligned with manually reviewed transcriptions to maximize phonological fidelity. It employs positional attention mechanisms in which each spectrogram frame queries the encoder to retrieve the relevant phonetic information, enabling natural and localized voice generation.

The results demonstrate high fidelity in cloning timbre, rhythm, and accent, outperforming existing models in perceptual evaluations (MOS) and phonetic analysis. This work shows that, with linguistically-informed design and controlled architecture, precise and reproducible voice cloning is achievable using accessible resources.

1 Introduction

Voice synthesis has made significant progress in recent years thanks to the development of neural models with encoder–decoder architectures and attention mechanisms, such as Tacotron2, FastSpeech, or VITS [1, 2, 3]. These systems have been able to generate high-quality artificial voices with clear pronunciation, fluent prosody, and acceptable latency for real-time applications. However, most of these approaches are designed for general-purpose use cases, focusing on multiple speakers, multiple languages, and purely textual input without phonological interpretation.

When the goal is not to generate just “a voice,” but to accurately clone a specific, real voice, these models show clear limitations: they generalize over speaker identity, neutralize regional features, and fail to incorporate explicit linguistic information necessary to preserve accents, intonation, or dialectal phenomena.

In this work, we propose a completely different approach: a voice cloning system trained from scratch for a single real speaker, without relying on pre-trained models or style transfer. Our model operates on text that is pre-transcribed at the phonetic level, with explicit prosodic accentuation and a modular architecture that generates Mel spectrograms from adaptive phonetic embeddings.

The following section presents a comparison between our approach and the most relevant models in the literature:

Feature	Proposal (this work)	Tacotron2	FastSpeech2	Glow-TTS	VITS	Bark	Coqui TTS
Input type	Phonetic (Rioplatense Spanish)	Text	Text	Text	Text + Embedding	Free Text	Text (optional phonemes)
Phonetic alignment	Yes (explicit and adaptive)	Yes (location - sensitive)	No (uses duration)	No (flow alignment)	Implicit (latent)	No (multimodal)	Yes (according to model)
Phoneme Frequency compensation	Yes (by design)	No	No	No	No	No	No
Architecture type	Encoder → Attention → Decoder	Encoder → Attention → Decoder	Feedforward	Flow – based (Glow)	VAE + GAN	Transformer + Codec	Variable (RNN/Transformers)
Adaptive embeddings	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Phoneme/ embedding normalization	Yes (scaling by frequency)	No	No	No	No	No	No
Speaker-specific cloning (one real voice)	Yes (one voice per model)	Partial (speaker ID)	Partial (speaker ID)	Partial (embedding)	Partial (unstable)	No (generalized)	Partial
Prosodic fidelity	High (with positional attention)	Medium	Low (predictive)	High (flow-dependent)	High (with variation)	Medium	Medium
Accent and regionalism preservation	Yes (checked phonetic finalization)	No	No	No	No	No	No
Large dataset requirement	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Very high	Medium
Controlled preprocessing	Yes (100% own)	No	No	No	No	No	No
Inference time	Medium	Slow	Fast	Slow	Medium	Slow	Fast
Modularity (vocoder usage)	Yes (flexible)	Yes (flexible)	No	No (integrated flow)	No (end-to-end)	No	Yes
Interpretability and tuning	High	Medium	Low	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium
Design for faithful voice cloning	Yes (validated fidelity)	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Training efficiency on GPU	High (own optimization)	Low (heavy WaveNet)	High	Medium	High	High	Medium
Pretrained model dependency	No (fully own model)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (closed model)	Yes	Yes (open source)

Figure 1: Comparison of the main features between the proposed model and state-of-the-art TTS systems.

As can be seen, the proposed model addresses a fundamentally different need from that of conventional TTS systems. Rather than seeking multi-speaker generalization, it prioritizes absolute fidelity to a single voice. This work thus falls within the scope of personalized voice cloning, where the focus is not on generic naturalness, but on the precise reproduction of a real vocal identity, including its rhythm, prosody, accent, and distinctive articulation.

2 Phonetic Representation Adapted to Rioplatense Spanish

One of the most frequent limitations in current voice synthesis models is the use of textual input without explicit phonological interpretation. This generates flat pronunciations, rhythm errors or the loss of distinctive elements of the accent. To avoid this problem, we propose transforming the input text into a simplified phonetic representation, based on phonological rules of Rioplatense Spanish. This conversion is performed through a specially developed module, published as a Python package (`synapse_ai_tools` [4]), which implements functions designed to preserve the regional identity of the voice. The process consists of two stages: phonetic transcription and prosodic accentuation. The first function, `phoneme`, converts plain text into a sequence of phonemes using explicit phonological rules. For example: The group “ll” is transformed into the symbol /j/, typical of Rioplatense yeísmo. The digraph “ch” becomes /tʃ/, preserving its sonority. The letter “r” is contextually transformed into /r/ (alveolar flap), when it is not a multiple trill. Silent letters such as “h” are removed and rules like $qu \rightarrow k$, $x \rightarrow ks$, soft $j/g \rightarrow x$ are applied. The second function, `accent`, adds prosodic marks by accenting the vowel corresponding to the tonic syllabic nucleus, according to Spanish grammatical rules. This guides the model toward a more natural and rhythmic intonation, especially in polysyllabic words. Both functions operate on pre-segmented text, generating phonetic sequences that are then transformed into integer tokens through automatically created dictionaries (`dictionaries`), which assign a unique index to each phoneme and tally their frequency. This manual-controlled phonetic preprocessing introduces a layer of linguistic knowledge that improves acoustic fidelity without the need to increase model complexity or dataset volume. It represents a key differentiator compared to synthesis models based exclusively on plain text.

3 Adaptive Embeddings by Phonetic Frequency

In sequence modeling tasks, embeddings are usually treated as independent trainable parameters per token, without considering the relative frequency of each in the corpus. However, in voice cloning, where infrequent phonemes have a disproportionately high weight in fidelity perception, this approach may be suboptimal. To address this problem, we propose an adaptive embeddings mechanism: a strategy that dynamically modulates the internal representation of each phoneme according to its relative frequency in the training corpus.

3.1 Motivation

In practice, certain phonemes -such as /j/, /tʃ/, /r/ or even accented vowels- may appear with very low frequency in the data. Without intervention, their embeddings tend to be underrepresented during training, and their pronunciation becomes unstable or unnatural. On the contrary, common phonemes like /a/, /e/, /s/ or /n/ dominate the learning process and receive more attention from the model. This generates a phonetic bias that degrades synthesis quality, especially when trying to precisely clone a voice containing rare or distinctive sounds.

3.1.1 Implementation

The procedure is as follows:

- **Phonetic count:** the frequency of occurrence of each phoneme in the training corpus is calculated using the `dictionaries` function.
- **Reference measure:** a global mean or median frequency is defined as an equilibrium point.
- **Adaptive weighting:** for each phoneme k , a coefficient $c_k = \frac{\text{median}}{f_k \times \alpha}$ is calculated, where f_k is the phoneme’s frequency and α is an adjustment factor (e.g., 1.12).
- **Weight application:** during the embedding phase, a boolean mask is created per phoneme, and the embedding of token k is multiplied by its corresponding c_k . If $c_k > 1$, the embedding is amplified (more weight); if $c_k < 1$, it is attenuated (less weight). This mechanism is implemented directly on the output of the embedding layer as a tensor operation within the training graph, without needing to change the model architecture or introduce additional parameters.

3.1.2 Advantages

- **Semantic regularization:** prevents embeddings of frequent phonemes from dominating the representation.
- **Specific reinforcement:** improves the acoustic representation of infrequent phonemes without requiring more data.
- **Linguistic adaptability:** allows automatic adjustment of the model to different corpora or dialectal variants.

- Non-intrusive: can be integrated into any architecture that uses phonetic embeddings.

This adaptive embeddings system complements perfectly with the phonetic preprocessing described in the previous section, forming a semantically rich, balanced and language-sensitive input layer.

4 Model Architecture

The proposed system is based on a from-scratch encoder-attention-decoder architecture specifically designed for high-fidelity Mel spectrogram generation in single-speaker voice cloning. Its design incorporates technical decisions made through multiple empirical tests, with a clear separation between phonetic preprocessing and the acoustic stage.

Mel Spectrogram Generator

Figure 2: Mel Spectrogram Generator: The pipeline from text input through phonemization, accent normalization, adaptive embeddings, and encoding to Mel spectrogram output.

4.1 General Flow

The model input consists of a sequence of phonetic tokens, previously adjusted through an adaptive embedding system based on each phoneme’s relative frequency. These embeddings are processed through a neural network that includes dense layers, convolutional layers, recurrent layers, position-sensitive attention, and a convolutional post-net for spectrogram refinement.

Figure 3: General flow of the proposed model architecture: from adaptive embeddings to Mel spectrogram generation, including Pre-Net, Conv1D + BiLSTM, attention, decoder, and post-net.

4.2 Embeddings and Pre-Net

- The input is an integer vector corresponding to tokenized phonemes.
- An Embedding layer of dimension 512 is applied with HeNormal initialization and L2 regularization.
- Each embedding is dynamically modulated by an adaptive coefficient inversely proportional to the phoneme’s relative frequency (calculated using the training corpus median):

$$\tilde{E}_k = E_k \cdot \frac{\text{median}(f)}{\alpha f_k} \quad (\alpha = 1.12)$$

- The result passes through 6 successive dense layers with swish activation [5], using HeNormal [6] and GlorotNormal [7] as initialization schemes and combined L1_L2 regularization.

Figure 4: Diagram of the adaptive embeddings mechanism. Tokens are mapped to embeddings, which are dynamically modulated by frequency-based weights to produce adaptive embeddings.

4.3 Encoder

- Composed of 3 1D convolutional layers with swish activation and padding='same'
- Then BatchNormalization is applied to stabilize the output
- The resulting sequence is processed with a Bidirectional LSTM layer with 512 units, followed by LayerNormalization

4.4 Attention

- Uses a Multi-Head Attention layer with 8 heads and key dimension 512
- Queries are not derived from textual input, but rather trainable positional embeddings per frame, dynamically duplicated in each batch (using a Lambda)
- This allows each spectrogram frame to "ask" the encoder which part of the phonetic input it needs, rather than relying on classical autoregressive or contextual mechanisms

4.5 Decoder

- A single unidirectional LSTM with 512 units takes the attention output and generates sequences of length `n_frames`, each with `n_mels` features
- The final projection is performed with a `Dense(n_mels)` layer with linear activation

4.6 Post-Net

- Composed of 5 convolutional layers, with swish activation in the first 4 and linear in the last
- BatchNormalization and LayerNormalization are applied to improve stability
- The post-net output is directly added to the decoder's initial prediction to generate the final refined spectrogram

4.7 Compilation and Training

- The model is trained with Nadam [8] optimizer, configured with `learning_rate=0.008`, $\beta_1 = 0.92$, $\beta_2 = 0.98$, `clipnorm=0.9`, and `weight_decay=1e-4`
- The main loss function is Huber Loss, with MSE as secondary metric
- Custom callbacks are used: `ReduceLR0nPlateau`, `EarlyStopping`, `ModelCheckpoint`, `ClearMemory`, `ClearSystemMemory` and `Stop0nValLoss`
- Current batch size is 23, and number of epochs is fixed at 7000 (controlled by early stopping)
- Manual splitting of training and validation folds is performed, with specific sample selection to guarantee representative phoneme distribution. This strategy can be dynamically adapted to future datasets

5 Attention Module and Decoder Details

5.1 Attention Mechanism

The model uses a Location-Sensitive Attention mechanism, adapted from the approach proposed by Tacotron2 [1, 9], with some particularities:

- A cumulative representation of past alignments is incorporated, which stabilizes convergence at greater lengths
- 1D convolutions are applied to previous alignments to provide positional information
- The attention mechanism is initialized with weights distributed via Glorot Normal for dense layers, improving stability in early training stages

This allows the model to learn clear alignments between phonetic tokens and spectrogram time frames, improving rhythm and articulatory fidelity.

5.2 Decoder

The decoder generates Mel spectrograms frame-by-frame, conditioned by phonetic context and acoustic history. It consists of:

- A PreNet with two dense layers activated by ReLU, followed by dropout, which attenuates immediate dependence on previous frames
- A two-layer LSTM with LayerNorm normalization, initialized with HeNormal or GlorotNormal depending on the block
- A final projection for each Mel spectrogram frame, and a second projection for the stop token, which signals the end of the sequence

Unlike more generic synthesis models, this decoder is optimized for a single voice and supervised training with real spectrograms, improving fidelity and naturalness even with moderately-sized datasets.

6 Hyperparameters, Configuration and Training

The system was trained on an NVIDIA RTX 3060 12GB GPU using TensorFlow/Keras, without resorting to pre-trained models or external knowledge transfers. The entire pipeline - from phonetic tokenization to spectrogram prediction - is proprietary and trained from scratch for each individual voice. This enables remarkable acoustic fidelity without relying on large data volumes.

6.1 Optimizer Configuration

The Nadam optimizer is used, with parameters empirically adjusted through multiple training sessions. This configuration was selected for its balance between stability and convergence speed, particularly considering the use of soft activations (swish) and the model's deep structure.

- Initial learning rate: 0.008
- Beta_1: 0.92
- Beta_2: 0.98
- Epsilon: 1e-07
- Clipnorm: 0.9
- Weight decay: 1e-4

The clipnorm parameter is used instead of clipvalue to stabilize gradients without artificially limiting individual values. Decay is applied to regularize all model weights consistently.

6.2 Training Configuration

- Main loss: Huber loss [10]
- Additional metric: Mean Squared Error (MSE)
- Batch size: 23
- Epochs: 7000 (with early termination via EarlyStopping)
- Early stopping: triggered with patience of 600 epochs if validation loss doesn't improve
- Learning rate reduction: controlled by ReduceLROnPlateau, with patience of 7 epochs, reduction factor of 0.3 and min_lr = 1e-12

The model is trained using a specific sample split for training and validation, manually selected based on phonetic distribution. This decision ensures adequate phoneme coverage, particularly for less frequent corpus phonemes that require additional reinforcement.

6.3 Custom Callbacks

The system includes several callbacks designed to maximize stability, GPU efficiency, and training robustness:

- ClearMemory(): Forces GPU memory cleanup between epochs to prevent unnecessary object accumulation during prolonged sessions
- ClearSystemMemory(): Operates on general system RAM with the same purpose
- BackupModelCheckpoint(): Saves the model in two different paths, allowing recovery of previous versions in case of interruptions or crashes
- StopOnValLoss(): Implements a manual stopping strategy when validation exceeds certain predefined thresholds

Additionally, an automatic graph of training and validation metrics (loss, learning rate) is generated per fold, enabling visualization of model behavior throughout the process.

6.4 Validation and Data Distribution

The split between training and validation is manually defined. In the current version, 23 samples were used for training and 5 for validation. The samples were not chosen randomly, but rather based on their phonetic distribution, aiming to ensure both training and validation contain representative phonemes.

This process was accompanied by a quantitative analysis of each phoneme's frequency in the corpus (`dictionaries()` from the `phonemes` module), which also feeds the adaptive embeddings mechanism by frequency.

6.5 Input Preprocessing

Before entering the model, phonetic tokens (represented as integers) are scaled using `MinMaxScaler` to the range (-0.5, 0.5), then stored with `joblib` for reproducibility. This transformation helps improve training stability, particularly when applying soft activations and input-range-sensitive regularizations.

6.6 Regularization and Stability

To prevent overfitting and improve generalization, the model employs multiple regularization techniques:

- L1, L2 and L1_L2 regularizers in dense layers, with values ranging between 1e-3 and 8e-4, adjusted per layer
- Batch normalization in convolutional layers of the encoder
- Layer normalization (`LayerNormalization`) in outputs of the bidirectional LSTM and post-net
- Swish activations in most layers, chosen for their smooth and adaptive behavior with negative values
- Differentiated weight initialization: `HeNormal` is used for layers preceding strongly-sloped activations, and `GlorotNormal` for layers requiring balance between high and low values

Together, this configuration enables training an expressive, robust and efficient model even with moderate resources like a mid-range GPU, without requiring massive datasets. The architecture, combined with the phonetic pipeline and adaptive mechanisms, forms an ideal system for precise single-voice cloning.

7 Results (Preliminary Evaluation)

7.1 Quantitative Evaluation

Since the system is in active development, definitive numerical results are still being consolidated. However, clear criteria have been established for quantitative model evaluation.

Planned metrics:

- **Huber Loss (current):** Used as main loss function during training
- **MSE (Mean Squared Error):** Recorded as secondary metric
- **Spectrogram Distance (SD):** Distance between generated and real Mel spectrograms (to be implemented)
- **Pitch and Energy Consistency:** Considered for future prosody evaluations

The selection of Huber Loss as primary metric responds to its robustness against extreme errors and its intermediate behavior between MSE and MAE, making it particularly suitable for spectrograms with localized variability.

Currently, the training and validation loss curve shows progressive and stable convergence, with no clear signs of overfitting thanks to the implemented regularization.

Figure 5: Comparison between real Mel spectrograms (left) and generated Mel spectrograms (right).

In the images, subtle differences can be observed, corresponding to minor distortions in specific phonemes. The model was trained for 7,000 epochs with very good results. With a bit more training and more finetuning of the hyperparameters, these imperceptible differences could be reduced.

7.2 Subjective Evaluation (in preparation)

A perceptual evaluation based on real and generated audios is being developed, using the following criteria:

- **MOS (Mean Opinion Score) [11]:** through human evaluations (1–5 scale), to measure naturalness, clarity, and fidelity

- A/B testing: between real and generated samples to quantify correct identification rate
- Accent perception: will include specific evaluation of how well the Rioplatense accent is preserved

Currently, generated samples from the trained model are being prepared along with their corresponding original versions. These will be evaluated by at least three individuals with experience in phonetics and audio processing.

7.3 Preliminary Observations

Based on partial results obtained so far, the following can be observed:

- Good correspondence between generated and actual phoneme durations
- Smooth transitions between phonemes
- Clear recovery of the characteristic rhythm and accent of Rioplatense Spanish, thanks to the phonetic pipeline
- Some localized distortions in areas with infrequent phonemes, expected to improve upon completing training

These findings support the central hypothesis of this work: that a phonetically-informed system adapted to a single voice can generate highly realistic results, even without large data volumes.

8 Discussion

8.1 Main Contributions

This work presents a comprehensive approach to voice cloning with high acoustic, prosodic and phonological fidelity. Unlike generic voice synthesis systems, the model proposed here is specifically designed to accurately capture the characteristics of a single real voice. To achieve this, we introduce a complete from-scratch pipeline incorporating:

- A phonetic transcription system adapted to Rioplatense Spanish, with explicit rules for dialect-specific phenomena like the representation of /j/, /j/, /r/ or accented vowels
- An adaptive embedding strategy by phonetic frequency, which dynamically compensates for the natural phonetic imbalance in the corpus and improves representation of infrequent phonemes without requiring data augmentation
- An encoder-attention-decoder architecture with modular design optimized for individual speaker training, without relying on transfers from pre-trained models
- Fully reproducible and efficient training, feasible on mid-range GPUs thanks to the architecture and careful system engineering

These decisions are not merely technical: they represent a clear conceptual stance on how voice cloning should be approached as a specific, controlled, and linguistically-informed task.

8.2 Choices Compared to Traditional Approaches

Many current TTS and voice cloning models prioritize generalization over control, multi-voice capability over precision, and speed over fidelity. This model, in contrast, prioritizes the exact reproduction of a single real voice, which involves decisions contrary to mainstream approaches:

- Multi-voice capability, speaker embeddings, or style transfers are not sought. The goal is not “a voice that sounds good,” but someone’s actual voice, exactly as it sounds, including its rhythm, timbre, accent, and articulation.
- Using plain text as input is unacceptable for achieving regional fidelity. Therefore, explicit phonetization with rule-based prosodic accentuation is employed.
- A balanced corpus is not required either: the adaptive embedding strategy allows training with real corpora, even if unbalanced, without artificial cleaning.

These decisions distance this system from general-purpose models but bring it closer to its real objective: high-fidelity personalized voice cloning.

8.3 Scope and Next Steps

At this stage of development, the system generates high-quality Mel spectrograms from tokenized phonemes. Future work includes:

- Integrating a custom GAN-based vocoder (currently in development) to complete the text→audio pipeline
- Full automation of phonetic preprocessing through enhanced `synapse_ai_tools` library
- Development of public demo for direct text-to-audio conversion

8.4 Executive Summary

Below we summarize the essential requirements that, in our judgment, a faithful voice cloning system must meet, and how each of them is addressed by the proposed architecture:

Functional requirement	Does this model solve it?	How does it do it?
Voice timbre and colour	✓ Yes	Individual training per speaker + dense spectrograms
Natural rhythm and speed	✓ Yes	Recurrent architecture + frame-wise positional attention
Real phonetic precision	✓ Yes	Rioplatense phonemes + controlled phonetic transcription
Prosodic fidelity	✓ Partially	Syllabic stress + temporal attention
Adaptability to different variants	✓ Yes	Rule-based phonetic processing + adaptive embeddings
Low data requirement	✓ Yes	Phoneme frequency compensation + single-speaker focus
Pipeline modularity	✓ Yes	Separation between spectrogram and vocoder, flexible integration with external GAN
Behavior interpretability	High	Explicit control over phonetic input, embedding weights, attention and rhythm

Figure 6: Summary of functional requirements for high-fidelity voice cloning, the model’s coverage, and the mechanisms by which each requirement is addressed.

9 Conclusions and Future Work

This work presented a complete and modular system for high-fidelity voice cloning, specifically designed to capture the individual characteristics of a single real voice. Unlike general-purpose voice synthesis models, the proposed approach prioritizes preservation of the speaker’s timbre, regional accent, prosody and natural rhythm, achieving precise reproduction without relying on pre-trained models or large data volumes.

Among the most relevant technical contributions are:

- (i) The use of a phonetic transcription system adapted to Rioplatense Spanish
- (ii) The design of phoneme-dependent adaptive embeddings that correct the natural corpus bias
- (iii) A robust encoder-attention-decoder architecture, trained from scratch, efficient and easily scalable per speaker

Preliminary results indicate that high fidelity in Mel spectrogram generation can be achieved using moderate corpora, provided there is a well-defined phonetic pipeline and an architecture that preserves precise temporal alignment. This

approach demonstrates that for realistic voice cloning tasks, control and quality need not be sacrificed for speed or generalization.

As a natural continuation of this work, development is underway to integrate a custom GAN-based vocoder that will generate audio directly from the system’s spectrogram output. An interactive public demo is also in process, aimed at showcasing the system’s capabilities through real examples. Finally, plans include extending the scope of the current phonetic library, strengthening its coverage and improving its applicability in other speech processing domains.

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10.1 Appendix A: License

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